

THE MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF INTERPERSONAL COMMUNICATION IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK.

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ABSTRACT This article is analyzes the relationship between the individual and society, the criteria for their evaluation, historical and social factors, and the main characteristics of interpersonal relationships not only in Uzbek but also in English.

Key words: interpersonal relationships, paremias, proverb

ANNOTATSIYA Ushbu maqolada shaxs va jamiyat o'rtasidagi munosabatlar, ularni baholash mezonlari, tarixiy va ijtimoiy omillar, shaxslararo munosabatlarning asosiy xususiyatlari nafaqat o'zbek, balki ingliz tilida ham tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Shaxslararo munosabatlar, paremiyalar, maqollar.

Introduction.

First of all, if we look at the essence of the concept of a person, a person is a creature that can understand, remember and think. An individual belongs to a person and serves to represent a member of society who is psychologically developed, distinguished from others by his or her personal characteristics and behavior, and who has existing behaviors and worldviews. A person is also a product of social and interpersonal relationships. The relationship between the individual and society plays an important role in the development of human philosophical thinking.

There are many concepts and philosophical views. Mythological and religious values were at the forefront of the relationship between the individual and society. Such social development is primarily an expression of one's perceptions of the world, consciousness, knowledge, influences and skills on the outside world. That is, it represents a "nature-human-society" relationship. Gradually, views on the

"human-society" relationship began to emerge. Religious, philosophical, and mythological views began to take shape. If we approach these two terms from a philosophical point of view, the relationship between "Man" and "Society" is a philosophical approach to the role of man in society, the essence of man and his characteristics. From a mythological point of view, the fantastic, imaginative expression of the relationship between man, individual, and society reflects the notion that consciousness is on a mythological level. In Eastern Indian philosophy, man is interpreted as a part of the "worldly soul", while in ancient Chinese philosophy, there are specific interpretations of man and society. Later, in the study of the relationship between man, society, and the individual, the philosophy formed in Ancient Greece formed the views of Socrates, Plato, Aristotle, Democritus, Aristotle, and many other philosophers on man, the individual, and society. The concept of Christianity emerged in the Middle Ages. In this one can meet the views of Augustine. Islam also pays special attention to the relationship between man and society. It is well known that views on modern and contemporary philosophy are also unique.

A. Maslow and K. Rodgers, the proponents of humanistic theory, believe that self-activation is the key to the development of the individual as a person. [2, 5]

Literature review.

A. Maslow and K. Rodgers, the proponents of humanistic theory, believe that the main feature of the development of the individual as a person is the desire for self-activation.

In the current process of globalization of social development, the problem of the relationship between the individual and society is gaining more and more attention. Historically, various religious and philosophical systems have taken a different approach to the issue of the individual. If we look at the philosophy of antiquity, in terms of social relations with the individual, in Christianity, the individual is understood as a special essence, "individual substance", a mental feature, synonymous with the intangible soul.

In the system of Islamic values, the teachings of mysticism, which is a specific direction of religious and philosophical thought, have also played an important role in the relationship between the individual and society. In the religious and philosophical views of the great mystics and founders of the sect, such as Abdukhalik Gisjivani, Ahmad Yassavi, Najmiddin Kubro, Bahauddin Naqshband, who grew up in Central Asia, the issues of socio-moral and spiritual maturity of man as one of the main aspects of mystical philosophy. the issue of public relations is clearly visible.

Among the many definitions and concepts, the description of the American psychologist G. Allport is noteworthy: thinking and behavior occur. ”[1, 12]

In the philosophy of the new era, the French philosopher R. Descartes paved the way for the formation of a dualistic idea of the individual. First of all, self-awareness is combined with the concept of "I".

In the later stages of social development, especially in the nineteenth century, the study of the relationship between the individual and society became a social necessity. The formation and content of the individual tried to scientifically substantiate the social sciences of the humanities: philosophy, pedagogy, psychology. If we look at the views and opinions of psychologists on the concept of personality, we can find many more colorful definitions. Leading Russian psychologists BG Ananaev, AN Leontiev, BF Lomov, SY Rubinstein have focused on the concepts of "person" and "individual" in their research. A.N. Leont'ev noted that a special quality, possessed by an individual, possesses systemic "non-emotional" qualities in the wave of human relations. Russian psychologist S.L. Rubinstein: “Man is individual due to his unique characteristics. His conscious attitude to those around him, to his being, to his activity, shows that he is a person. In light of these considerations, it is clear that all actions are based on an individual approach, and that each person is an individual.

Research methodology.

The nature of interpersonal relationships is influenced by personal characteristics such as gender, ethnicity, age, character, health, occupation, experience with people, self-awareness, need for communication, and so on. Stages of development of interpersonal relations:

- 1) the stage of acquaintance - the first stage - the emergence of interactions, mutual understanding and evaluation between people, which determines the nature of the relationship;
- 2) the period of friendship - the emergence of interpersonal relationships, the rational relationship of people to each other (people who interact understand each other's values and shortcomings) and on an emotional level (the emergence of relevant experiences, emotional attitudes, etc.);
- 3) friendship - convergence of views and support for each other; characterized by confidence.

Analysis and results.

Communication is the interaction between two or more people in the exchange of information in the form of knowledge or evaluation. The fact that communication is understood in the form of the production of something that unites people in the process of interaction and interaction means that language as a means of communication. Language provides communication between communicators. The person who informs the information by encoding it according to the essence of the words chosen for this purpose, also discloses the code of this essence, that is, reveals its meaning and changes his behavior on the basis of this information. otherwise the person receiving the information will also understand.

Russian psychologist S.L. Rubinstein: "Man is individual due to his unique characteristics. The fact that he is conscious of his surroundings, of being, of doing something, shows that he is a person." [3, 18]

When people enter into a conversation, the goal is to ask questions, to order, to beg, to explain something, to influence others, to explain that to them. The purpose of communication is to reflect the person's need for collaboration. In this case,

communication is manifested as interpersonal interactions, that is, a set of connections and interactions that occur in the course of human interaction.

Conclusion

Communication is a process born of the need for collaboration. According to A.B. Petrovskiy, communication is a multifaceted process of establishing and developing communication between people, which is the result of the needs of cooperation. But communication is not just a process born of the need to work together, it is also a process of interpersonal interaction.

Communication is a type of communication in which people communicate their feelings, ideas, emotions, and information face to face. This can be in writing or orally. According to the means of communication, it is direct and indirect, in which information is exchanged with the help of the natural organs of living things, such as hands, head, body, sound - this is direct, if special in the organization of communication and exchange of information. When weapons and means are used, this communication is called indirect.

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